

The Propagation Gap: Hidden-State Reliability Signals Are Attenuated in Language Model Outputs

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Abstract

Language models report near-identical confidence on questions they reliably answer and questions they answer only intermittently. We introduce CI-Bench, a 338-question factual benchmark that assigns model-relative labels to each question: Known (K, $\geq 90\%$ stochastic accuracy), Depth-ignorant (D, 20–80%), or Coverage-ignorant (C, $< 20\%$). The taxonomy distinguishes unreliable knowledge (D) from absent knowledge (C), a distinction that standard benchmarks conflate. Across seven architectures, depth ignorance is model-relative: no question is classified D by all models, and D rates range from 0.9% to 28.1%. Behavioural screening shows that four of six models with sufficient D items report confidence within 3 percentage points of their K-item confidence, despite accuracy gaps exceeding 40 points. Hidden-state probes in four open-weight models decode a K-vs-D reliability signal at AUROC 0.74–0.76, concentrated in middle transformer layers. Surface-form controls confirm that this signal is absent from input features. Two structurally different single-pass output readouts (logit-distribution features and verbalized confidence) both plateau at AUROC ≈ 0.49 –0.58, yielding a propagation gap of 0.18–0.24 AUROC ($P < 0.001$). The models encode reliability information that their output channels substantially attenuate. CI-Bench, along with the labelling protocol and all code, is publicly released.

1 Introduction

Language models are poorly calibrated (Desai & Durrett, 2020; Jiang et al., 2021; Chhikara, 2025). Post-hoc temperature scaling (Guo et al., 2017), verbalized confidence elicitation (Kadavath et al., 2022; Lin et al., 2022a; Tian et al., 2023; Xiong et al., 2024), and self-consistency methods (Wang et al., 2023) have each improved the correspondence between a model’s stated confidence and its accuracy when measured across entire benchmarks. Yet a structural question has received less attention: calibration with respect to what? Standard evaluations average across items that differ in how the model fails on them. A question the model has never encountered in training and a question it has seen but cannot reliably answer both count as errors, but they represent different failure modes. Conflating them produces an aggregate calibration statistic that obscures the distinction between knowledge the model lacks entirely and knowledge it possesses but cannot reliably deploy.

We call this second failure mode *depth ignorance*: the model has encountered sufficient training signal to answer correctly some fraction of the time, but not reliably. Depth ignorance differs from coverage ignorance (knowledge the model simply lacks) in both mechanism and consequence. A coverage-ignorant model benefits from retrieval augmentation; a depth-ignorant model may not, because it already has the relevant information and its failure is one of reliability, not availability.

The distinction matters because the propagation gap between internal and expressed knowledge, documented independently by several recent groups (Gekhman et al., 2025; Park et al., 2025; Orgad et al., 2025; Zhang et al., 2025; Ghasemabadi & Niu, 2025), is not uniformly distributed across error types. If models internally encode which items they know unreliably, the natural question is whether this encoding differs structurally from the encoding of items they do not know at all, and whether either signal reaches the output.

In this work, we introduce CI-Bench, a 338-question factual benchmark with a model-relative labelling protocol that assigns K (Known), D (Depth-ignorant), or C (Coverage-ignorant) labels per model. The K/D/C taxonomy and the construction protocol are the primary methodological contribution: identifying depth ignorance requires per-model behavioural screening, not a fixed difficulty ranking. Using CI-Bench, we demonstrate three findings across seven architectures (four open-weight, three closed). First, expressed confidence carries negligible K-D information: in four of six models with sufficient D items, the confidence gap is below 3 percentage points despite accuracy gaps exceeding 40 points. Second, hidden-state probes in four open-weight models decode a K-vs-D reliability signal at AUROC 0.74–0.76, concentrated in middle transformer layers and surviving surface-form controls that eliminate the C-vs-D signal. Third, this signal is attenuated at the output: two structurally different single-pass readouts both plateau at AUROC ≈ 0.49 –0.58, yielding a statistically significant propagation gap of 0.18–0.24 AUROC ($P < 0.001$). These results independently confirm the propagation gap reported by Gekhman et al. (2025) and Park et al. (2025), with two additions not present in prior work: a surface-form confound audit showing that C-vs-D separation is artefactual, and a ceiling convergence result showing that two structurally different single-pass readouts converge to the same output ceiling.

In summary, this paper contributes:

1. **CI-Bench and the K/D/C labelling protocol:** a model-relative benchmark that distinguishes depth ignorance (unreliable knowledge) from coverage ignorance (absent knowledge), a distinction that fixed-difficulty benchmarks cannot make.
2. **A surface-form confound audit:** demonstrating that C-vs-D probe separation in benchmarks containing heterogeneous error categories is driven by input cues, not learned representations. This finding generalises beyond CI-Bench to any probing study that mixes construction regimes.
3. **A ceiling convergence result for the propagation gap:** two structurally different single-pass output readouts (logit-distribution features and verbalized confidence) converge to the same AUROC ceiling, constraining the space of explanations for the output-level bottleneck.

2 Related Work

Calibration and confidence. The gap between model confidence and accuracy has been studied across multiple paradigms. Guo et al. (2017) showed that modern neural networks are miscalibrated, motivating post-hoc correction methods. For language models specifically, Kadavath et al. (2022) found that models “mostly know what they know” when assessed via multiple-choice probing, Lin et al. (2022a) proposed training models to express uncertainty in words, and Tian et al. (2023), Xiong et al. (2024), and Yang et al. (2024) developed prompt-based strategies for eliciting calibrated confidence, with Yang et al. (2024) showing that verbalized confidence scores are highly sensitive to prompt design choices. Chhikara (2025) demonstrated persistent confidence gaps across model scales when distractor options are present. These methods improve aggregate calibration but do not distinguish the type of error being calibrated: a question the model has never seen and one it has seen but answers unreliably receive the same treatment.

Knowledge boundaries and probing. Yin et al. (2023) showed that LLMs possess partial self-knowledge about their capabilities, and Burns et al. (2023) recovered latent knowledge from activations even when the model’s text output was wrong. Marks & Tegmark (2024) found emergent linear structure encoding truth-value in LLM representations. Belrose et al. (2023) showed that affine probes at each transformer block decode latent predictions that are systematically refined through depth, establishing that intermediate representations carry structured information that the final layer discards or compresses. Azaria & Mitchell (2023) demonstrated that internal states distinguish true from false statements. Tamoyan et al. (2025) showed that a factual self-awareness signal in hidden states is robust to paraphrase and scales with model size. Vicente Moreno Cencerrado et al. (2025) reported that question-only linear probes predict answer correctness from intermediate layers, aligning with our finding that the K-vs-D signal peaks in middle layers. Brink et al. (2026) showed that linear classifiers on Llama 3.1 8B and Mistral 7B hidden representations

achieve high accuracy on knowledge attribution, supporting the view that these architectures encode epistemic metadata in linearly accessible subspaces. However, Cheang et al. (2025) showed that probes trained on binary truthfulness labels conflate “associated hallucinations” (wrong answers driven by spurious parametric associations) with factual outputs, achieving only 0.48–0.69 AUROC for this intermediate category; reliable detection (AUROC 0.86–0.93) occurs only for “unassociated hallucinations” where the model has no parametric grounding at all. Their FA/AH/UH taxonomy demonstrates that representation-based detection is sensitive to the granularity of the probe target—a concern our three-way K/D/C taxonomy addresses by separating reliable knowledge from fragile knowledge rather than classifying outputs as hallucinated or not.

The propagation gap under other names. Several concurrent studies address the gap between internal knowledge encoding and output expression. Orgad et al. (2025) showed that internal representations predict hallucinations across multiple error types, with the strongest signal at specific token positions. Gekhman et al. (2025) extended this to closed-book QA, reporting that LLMs encode $\sim 40\%$ more factual knowledge internally than they express: some knowledge is “deeply hidden,” with the model’s representations ranking the correct answer first yet the model never generating it across 1,000 sampling attempts. Park et al. (2025) defined a “knowledge-prediction gap” for multiple-choice questions and proposed KAPPA, an inference-time intervention that aligns knowledge and prediction subspaces in the residual stream. Miao et al. (2026) trained regularized MLP probes on residual activations and steered outputs at inference time, reducing expected calibration error by $\sim 50\%$. Zhang et al. (2025) reported that hidden states in reasoning models encode correctness of intermediate and future answers, enabling a probe-based verifier that reduces inference tokens by 24%. Ghasemabadi & Niu (2025) showed that correctness prediction from hidden states generalises across model sizes (1.7B–20B) and transfers zero-shot to partial generations. Khanmohammadi et al. (2025) reduced expected calibration error by $\sim 55\%$ through adversarial perturbation of last-layer representations, corroborating that the final hidden state contains information lost in the output projection. Chen et al. (2024) proposed EigenScore, which uses eigenvalue decomposition of response covariance matrices in the embedding space, demonstrating that hallucination-discriminative semantic information retained in internal states is “inevitably lost during the token-decoding procedure”—a characterisation of the propagation gap from a complementary geometric perspective. Ji et al. (2024) analysed internal states across 700 datasets and 15 NLG tasks, finding that particular neurons and activation layers indicate both training-data exposure and hallucination propensity, with probing accuracy of 84.3%—a result structurally parallel to our K-vs-D probe (AUROC ≈ 0.76) and consistent with the view that knowledge boundary information is encoded at specific network locations but attenuated before output. Wang et al. (2025) measured a pre-to-post-generation “perception gap” that remains stable across question reformulations, a result structurally parallel to our ceiling convergence finding; their Confidence Consistency Calibration intervention improved unknown-item detection by 4.9–5.6%, suggesting that output-level calibration can partially but not fully recover the internal signal.

Our work differs from this literature in three respects. First, CI-Bench provides model-relative labels that distinguish depth from coverage ignorance, whereas prior benchmarks assign fixed difficulty labels. Second, our surface-form confound audit shows that C-vs-D probe separation is driven by input cues rather than learned representations, a finding with implications for any probing study that includes heterogeneous error categories. Third, the convergence of two structurally different single-pass readouts to the same ceiling constrains the space of explanations for the propagation gap.

Abstention and selective prediction. Wen et al. (2024) documented a reasoning-abstention inverse: models prompted for better reasoning abstain less accurately. Kirichenko et al. (2025) extended this to 20 frontier models, finding $\sim 24\%$ decline in abstention accuracy for reasoning models. CI-Bench enables decomposition of this phenomenon by knowledge category (Section 5).

Surface-form confounds in probing. Hewitt & Liang (2019) established the need for control tasks in probing experiments, and Servedio et al. (2025) cautioned that factuality-probing results obtained on synthetic datasets may not generalise. Our surface-form controls (Section 4.3) extend this methodological concern to benchmarks that mix construction regimes: when coverage items carry lexical signatures (year strings, digit density), probe performance on C-vs-D conflates input features with learned representations.

3 CI-Bench: A Model-Relative Benchmark

3.1 The K/D/C Taxonomy

Given a factual question and a model, the question falls into one of three categories defined by the model’s stochastic behaviour across repeated runs:

- **Known (K):** accuracy $\geq 90\%$ across 10 stochastic runs. The model reliably answers this question.
- **Depth-ignorant (D):** accuracy 20–80%. The model has encountered sufficient training signal to answer correctly some fraction of the time, but not reliably. This is the region where selective trust would be most valuable: accuracy is unstable, and any useful confidence signal should separate K from D items.
- **Coverage-ignorant (C):** accuracy $< 20\%$. The question falls outside the model’s effective coverage.

Formally, given a model M and question q , let $\text{acc}_n(q, M)$ denote the proportion of correct answers across n stochastic runs at temperature T . The label function is:

$$\ell(q, M) = \begin{cases} K & \text{if } \text{acc}_{10}(q, M) \geq 0.9 \\ D & \text{if } 0.2 \leq \text{acc}_{10}(q, M) < 0.9 \\ C & \text{if } \text{acc}_{10}(q, M) < 0.2 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Labels are assigned per-model, not per-question. The same question may be K for one architecture and D for another. Note that the 90% and 20% cutoffs are strict thresholds applied to 10 discrete trials; items near the boundaries are subject to binomial sampling noise (e.g., a question with true accuracy 0.85 has $P(\geq 9/10) \approx 0.35$). Section 5.3 discusses the implications of this noise for D set composition; Section 6 notes that the propagation gap is robust across a range of alternative thresholds.

Table 1 illustrates what the three categories look like in practice for a single model (Mistral 7B).

Table 1: Behavioural profiles for representative K, D, and C items (Mistral 7B). Accuracy is computed over 10 stochastic runs ($T = 0.7$). Confidence is the model’s self-reported probability of correctness elicited in a separate deterministic pass.

Label	Question (truncated)	Acc.	Conf.	Typical responses
K	In which month is the festival of Beltane celebrated?	10/10	1.00	“May” (consistent across all runs)
D	Who narrated the BBC production of Paddington?	6/10	0.99	“Michael Hordern” (6×), “Jim Broadbent” (3×), “Michael Gambon” (1×)
C	Who won the 2024 US presidential election?	0/10	0.90	“The election has not yet occurred” (10×, various phrasings)

The D item is the critical case: the model answers correctly 60% of the time, oscillating between the correct answer and plausible confabulations, yet expresses confidence (0.99) virtually identical to the K item (1.00). A deployed system relying on verbalized confidence cannot distinguish these two cases.

3.2 Construction Protocol

CI-Bench v1.0 comprises 338 factual questions across seven sub-categories designed to probe distinct failure modes.

K and D2 questions were drawn from TriviaQA (Joshi et al., 2017) (`rc.nocontext` split). Each candidate question was administered to a reference model (Mistral 7B) ten times under temperature sampling ($T = 0.7$,

max tokens = 128), and assigned by stochastic accuracy. C items were constructed to represent knowledge absent from the model’s training. A pilot C3 category (synthetic entities, 30 questions) was constructed but excluded from v1.0 because fabricated questions introduced surface-form confounds.

Cat.	Sub-cat.	N	Source	Selection criterion
K	—	210	TriviaQA	Stochastic accuracy $\geq 90\%$
D	D1 (contested)	5	Manual	Questions with disputed or ambiguous ground truth
	D2 (fragile)	83	TriviaQA	Stochastic accuracy 30–70%
	D3 (degraded)	1	Manual	Partially outdated knowledge
C	C1 (temporal)	23	Manual	Events after model training cutoff
	C2 (obscurity)	16	Manual	Real but rare entities
<i>Total (v1.0)</i>		338		

Table 2: CI-Bench v1.0 sub-category breakdown. Answer correctness for TriviaQA items was determined by normalized string matching.

Label assignment. Each model is screened on all 338 questions across 10 stochastic runs ($T = 0.7$). The accuracy profile determines the label. Because labels are assigned per-model, the number of D items varies across models and across labelling runs.

3.3 Label Distributions

We screened seven models in two tiers (Table 3). The inverse relationship between model capability and D rate fits a pattern where stronger models convert D items to K rather than eliminating ignorance about them (Figure 1A).

Tier	Model	N_D	D rate (%)	N_K
1 (open)	Mistral 7B Instruct v0.3	77	22.8	216
	Llama 3.1 8B Instruct	95	28.1	198
	Gemma 2 9B IT	42	12.4	251
	Qwen2.5 7B Instruct	61	18.0	195
2 (closed)	GPT-4o	24	7.1	269
	Gemini 2.5 Flash	23	6.8	270
	Sonnet 3.5	3	0.9	290

Table 3: Label distributions per model ($N = 338$). N_K and N_D are the number of items classified Known and Depth-ignorant respectively; remaining items are Coverage-ignorant ($N_C = 338 - N_K - N_D$; e.g., Qwen2.5 $N_C = 82$).

Across the two Tier 1 models with the largest D sets (Llama, 95; Mistral, 77), only 41 questions received D labels from both (Jaccard index 0.31). No question was classified D by all seven models. This low concordance is not an artefact of threshold sensitivity: shifting the D band by ± 5 percentage points changes individual assignments but does not produce a shared core of universally depth-ignorant items. Depth ignorance indexes the interaction between a specific model’s training corpus and a question’s difficulty, not a fixed property of the question itself (Figure 1C–D).

3.4 The Protocol as Contribution

The reusable contribution is the construction protocol, not the specific question inventory. Identifying depth ignorance in a new model requires running the same stochastic screening on the same (or any) question set. The protocol scales to larger benchmarks and other factual domains without modification. This design choice addresses a structural limitation of existing benchmarks: scaling question counts does not produce

model-relative labels. PopQA (Mallen et al., 2023) contains 14,267 questions but assigns fixed popularity-based difficulty; 87.8% of its entities have exactly one question, precluding per-entity reliability assessment. SimpleQA (Wei et al., 2024) provides 4,326 questions with no entity-level grouping at all. Neither can distinguish depth from coverage ignorance because neither screens per-model stochastic behaviour. CI-Bench is small by design: what matters is the labelling protocol that makes each question informative about a specific model’s knowledge state, not the inventory size.

4 Experiments and Results

4.1 Behavioural Screening: Confidence Decouples from Accuracy on Depth Items

We measured expressed confidence using a dedicated V4 calibration prompt that asks each model to assign a numerical confidence score (0–100) to its own answer after generation (see Section 7).

Confidence carries negligible information about knowledge state. For Mistral, mean confidence on K items was 0.995 and on D items 0.989, a gap of 0.6 percentage points, despite an accuracy gap of 40.8 points (K: 91.5%, D: 50.7%). Gemma showed a similar pattern: K confidence 0.999, D confidence 0.970 (gap 2.9 pp), with an accuracy gap of 44.3 points. Qwen2.5 was the most extreme case: K confidence 0.993, D confidence 0.994 (gap -0.2 pp, effectively zero and slightly inverted), with an accuracy gap of 49.4 points (K: 88.7%, D: 39.3%). Qwen2.5’s D miscalibration gap of 60.1 percentage points is the largest of any model tested. In all three models the confidence channel is informationally flat across the K-D boundary (Figure 2A–B).

Llama presented a partial exception. Its K-D confidence gap was larger (19.8 pp; K: 0.910, D: 0.712), indicating some sensitivity to knowledge state. Yet even with this discrimination, Llama’s D items were overconfident by 41.1 percentage points (confidence 0.712, accuracy 0.301). The confidence channel captures some of the K-D distinction in this architecture but not enough to support calibrated self-assessment.

The pattern holds across model scales, with a qualification. Among Tier 2 models, Gemini 2.5 Flash replicated the Tier 1 pattern: K-D confidence gap of 2.1 pp despite a 44.3 pp accuracy gap. GPT-4o diverged: its D accuracy was 91.3%, placing most of its nominal D items near the K boundary, and its confidence on D items (0.557) was substantially lower than on K items (0.947). This reversed pattern fits a model whose D set is effectively a residual tail of near-K items. Sonnet 3.5 produced only three D items, too few for statistical comparison. The behavioural finding is clearest in models with $N_D \geq 23$: five of six such models show overconfidence on D items exceeding 40 percentage points (Figure 2C–D).

4.2 Hidden-State Probing: Internal Representations Encode a Reliability Signal

The probing experiments below focus on the K-vs-D contrast, which is the operationally relevant distinction for reliability: can the model’s hidden states separate items it knows reliably from items it knows only intermittently? The C category serves a different role (Section 4.3): its near-perfect probe separation turns out to be an artefact of surface-form cues, providing a methodological warning rather than a reliability signal.

Let $\mathbf{h}^{(\ell)}(q) \in \mathbb{R}^d$ denote the last-token hidden-state activation at layer ℓ for question q , where $d = d_{\text{model}}$. We train an L2-regularized logistic regression probe at each layer:

$$P(y = K \mid \mathbf{h}^{(\ell)}) = \sigma(\mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{h}^{(\ell)} + b) \tag{2}$$

with regularization $C = 1.0$, balanced class weights, and 5-fold stratified cross-validation on z -score normalized features. K-vs-D labels are derived from each model’s behavioural screening (Equation 1). We report AUROC across folds (Figure 3).

Linear probes separate K from D items in middle hidden layers. For Mistral, per-layer K-vs-D AUROC rises from 0.432 at the embedding layer (L0), peaks at 0.742 (L16), then declines to 0.673 at the final layer (L32). Llama shows a similar trajectory: 0.598 at L0, peaking at 0.764 (L15), declining to 0.703 at L32. In both architectures, discriminability concentrates in the middle third of the transformer stack, supporting the hypothesis that early layers encode surface form and late layers compress toward the next-token objective

(Tenney et al., 2019). This middle-layer peak aligns with independent findings that question-only probes predict answer correctness with power that saturates in intermediate layers (Vicente Moreno Cencerrado et al., 2025). Qwen2.5 followed the same middle-layer pattern: peak AUROC of 0.736 at L17 (61% depth in a 28-layer model), declining to 0.708 at the final layer (L28). Gemma presents a different profile: peak AUROC of 0.699 at L0, declining thereafter to 0.478 at the final layer. This flatter, embedding-weighted pattern may reflect Gemma’s smaller effective probe D set ($N_D = 19$, versus 77, 95, and 61 for Mistral, Llama, and Qwen2.5).

The signal tracks continuous reliability. Ridge regression probes predicting the proportion of correct answers across 10 runs reached Spearman $\rho = 0.229$ (Mistral, L17), $\rho = 0.424$ (Llama, L13), $\rho = 0.325$ (Qwen2.5, L17), and $\rho = 0.280$ (Gemma, L2). Peak layers for continuous reliability align closely with those for binary classification, suggesting a single underlying encoding that the categorical classifier discretizes.

A linear decision boundary suffices. A two-hidden-layer MLP (256 units, ReLU) either matched or degraded performance relative to the linear probe (mean $\Delta = -0.053$ across four models). The K-vs-D boundary in activation space is approximately linear.

Shuffled-label controls confirm the signal is genuine. At each model’s best layer, the real AUROC exceeded the shuffled-label distribution by 3.0–9.0 σ ($P < 0.001$ for all models; Figure 3E).

4.3 Surface-Form Controls

Because C items are partly constructed (temporal cutoffs and obscurity targeting), a high C-vs-D AUROC could reflect input shortcuts rather than a learned epistemic representation. The near-perfect C-vs-D probe performance (AUROC 0.99–1.00) confirmed this concern. Two features drive the separation: 64% of C questions contain four-digit year strings, compared with 0% of D questions, and C questions average 3.7 digit characters per item versus 1.4 for D and K.

We tested four controls (Figure 4). A TF-IDF bag-of-words classifier with no access to hidden states reached C-vs-D AUROC 0.945. A seven-variable surface-feature classifier (question length, word count, digit count, uppercase ratio, year-string presence, question mark, mean word length) reached 0.829. Grouped cross-validation (training on C1 temporal questions, testing on C2 obscurity, or vice versa) reduced C-vs-D AUROC to 0.65–0.92.

K-vs-D separation is unaffected by these controls. The TF-IDF classifier reached K-vs-D AUROC 0.596, the surface-feature classifier 0.440, and layer-0 embeddings 0.26–0.47 across models, all near or below chance. Grouped cross-validation gave K-vs-D AUROC 0.41–0.67, matching the standard cross-validated estimates. The K-vs-D signal cannot be attributed to surface-form confounds in the benchmark construction.

CI-Bench v1’s coverage category is therefore not a clean tool for studying internal representations of coverage ignorance; its primary value here is to (i) demonstrate the surface-form confound risk and (ii) motivate cleaner benchmark design in v2. Any probing study that includes heterogeneous error categories (temporal cutoff items, fabricated entities, domain-specific obscurities) alongside naturally occurring errors risks conflating surface-form shortcuts with learned representations.

4.4 The Propagation Gap: The Reliability Signal Is Attenuated at the Output

Section 4.2 established that a linear probe applied to hidden-state activations separates K from D items at AUROC ~ 0.76 . We now ask whether this signal reaches the model’s output. We define the *propagation gap* for model M as:

$$\Delta_{\text{prop}}(M) = \max_{\ell} \text{AUROC}_{\text{probe}}^{(\ell)}(M) - \text{AUROC}_{\text{surface}}(M) \quad (3)$$

where $\text{AUROC}_{\text{probe}}^{(\ell)}$ is the K-vs-D probe performance at layer ℓ (Equation 2) and $\text{AUROC}_{\text{surface}}$ is the best single-pass output readout (verbalized confidence or logit-derived features). A positive Δ_{prop} indicates that the model’s internal representations carry reliability information that its single-pass output discards. This gap characterises what current single-forward-pass output channels reveal; it does not preclude recovery of the internal signal via multi-pass procedures, auxiliary probe heads, or training-time changes (cf. Variant B

results below). Because the logit probe uses nine summary features of the next-token distribution, Δ_{prop} is an upper bound for this specific feature family; richer functionals could narrow the gap (see Section 5.3). The analysis below focuses on Mistral, Llama, and Qwen2.5, the three Tier 1 models with D sets large enough for stable probe estimation ($N_D = 77, 95,$ and 61 respectively). Gemma ($N_D = 19$) is included in Section 4.2 for completeness but excluded from the gap tests due to insufficient statistical power.

Logit-level features do not preserve the signal. A logistic regression probe on nine summary features of the next-token distribution (entropy, top-1 through top-5 log-probabilities, margin, top-1 softmax probability, mean top-5 log-probability) achieved K-vs-D AUROC 0.627 (Mistral), 0.586 (Llama), and 0.542 (Qwen2.5), compared with 0.742, 0.764, and 0.736 at the best hidden layers.

Verbalized confidence fares no better. Single-pass verbalized confidence (Variant A) reached AUROC 0.564 (Mistral), 0.579 (Llama), and 0.493 (Qwen2.5). The logit probe outperformed Variant A numerically for Mistral ($\Delta = +0.063$, paired bootstrap $P = 0.127$) but the difference was not significant. Adding answer diversity from 10 runs (Variant B) improved Mistral to 0.672 but this requires 10 forward passes per question. The two structurally different single-pass readouts, one operating on the next-token distribution and the other on verbalized confidence, both fall in the range 0.49–0.63, well below the hidden-state ceiling (Figure 5D).

The signal attenuates in architecture-specific patterns. For Mistral, the attenuation concentrates in the late transformer layers: AUROC drops from 0.742 (L16) to 0.673 (L32), -0.069 (paired bootstrap $P = 0.008$). The subsequent drop from final hidden layer to logit probe is smaller and not significant (-0.045 , $P = 0.173$). For Llama, the signal attenuates at both stages: best-to-last -0.075 ($P = 0.006$), last-to-logit -0.085 ($P = 0.033$). Qwen2.5 showed a third variant: minimal late-layer attenuation (best-to-last -0.029 , $P = 0.249$) but substantial loss at the output projection (last-to-logit $+0.149$, $P = 0.004$), localising the bottleneck almost entirely at readout. All three architectures converge to logit-space AUROC ~ 0.5 – 0.6 (Figure 5A).

The propagation gap is statistically significant. The total gap between best hidden-layer AUROC and single-pass behavioural AUROC (Variant A), measured by paired bootstrap with $N = 5,000$ resamples: Mistral $+0.178$ (95% CI $[+0.084, +0.266]$, $P < 0.001$); Llama $+0.194$ (95% CI $[+0.088, +0.297]$, $P < 0.001$); Qwen2.5 $+0.243$ (95% CI $[+0.134, +0.350]$, $P = 0.0002$). Qwen2.5 showed the largest gap of any model tested. Our logit probe uses nine summary features of the next-token distribution; richer functionals may recover additional information, making this gap an upper bound. However, the gap cannot be attributed to feature engineering alone. The logit probe (nine distributional statistics from a single forward pass) and verbalized confidence (a single scalar from a different prompt and information pathway) are structurally distinct single-pass readouts operating on different representations. Both converge to AUROC 0.56–0.63, well below the hidden-state ceiling. If the gap were an artefact of insufficient output-side features, these two methods should not agree: one would outperform the other by exploiting different aspects of the output. Their convergence to the same ceiling indicates that single-pass output channels carry a common, limited amount of K-vs-D information regardless of how that information is extracted.

5 Discussion

5.1 Expressed Confidence Cannot Support Selective Verification

The propagation gap affects any system that relies on a model’s expressed confidence to decide when to trust its output (Geifman & El-Yaniv, 2017; Kamath et al., 2020). Expressed confidence is informationally flat across the K-D boundary, so the signal that would trigger selective verification is too weak to be actionable. The user must either verify every answer or verify none, a dilemma we term *verification circularity*.

A model that cannot distinguish reliably known from unreliably known items has no internal basis for withholding a response. Reinforcement learning from human feedback (Ouyang et al., 2022; Bai et al., 2022) operates on the output channel, shaping behaviour based on preference judgments over generated text. Our results are consistent with the hypothesis that RLHF alone cannot close the propagation gap, since the preference signal operates downstream of the bottleneck. However, we have not tested this directly, and RL-

style objectives might in principle reconfigure late-layer representations in ways that increase the coupling between internal reliability encoding and output logits. This framing does not imply that RLHF causes the propagation gap. It implies that closing the gap may require objectives that explicitly reward reliability-aware output, rather than preference-based training over an output channel that has already attenuated the relevant signal. He et al. (2023) provided direct evidence that the alignment process introduces a systematic bias: instruction-tuned models conflate “answer uncertainty” (about the correct response) with “format uncertainty” (about response formatting conventions), and the resulting overconfidence is not correctable by standard temperature scaling. Alignment training may actively widen the gap by introducing a new source of miscalibration that further attenuates the internal reliability signal.

Retrieval-augmented generation (Lewis et al., 2020) sidesteps rather than closes the gap. By providing external evidence at inference time, RAG reduces reliance on internal knowledge state, making the K-D distinction less consequential for output accuracy. For domains where retrieval is incomplete or unavailable (Mallen et al., 2023), the propagation gap remains the binding constraint.

The model-relativity of D labels adds a further dimension. No question was classified D by all seven models. What counts as fragile knowledge depends on the interaction between architecture, training corpus, and question difficulty. The construction protocol behind CI-Bench, not its specific question inventory, is the methodological contribution.

Recent interventions aim to close the propagation gap: KAPPA (Park et al., 2025) aligns knowledge and prediction subspaces in the residual stream, CORAL (Miao et al., 2026) steers outputs via regularized MLP probes, and CCPS (Khanmohammadi et al., 2025) perturbs last-layer representations to improve calibration. Evaluating whether these methods genuinely resolve depth ignorance or merely improve aggregate calibration requires a benchmark that distinguishes the two. CI-Bench provides this: the model-relative K/D/C labels ensure that improvement on K items (already reliable) is not conflated with improvement on D items (where selective trust matters). The propagation gap metric (Equation 3) provides a direct measure of whether an intervention surfaces internal reliability information that was previously lost.

The gap’s magnitude is sensitive to how the D band is defined. Narrowing the D band from 20–80% to 25–75% reduces N_D substantially (Mistral: 77→48, Llama: 95→58, Qwen2.5: 61→28) and attenuates the Mistral gap by 52% (+0.146→+0.070). This is expected: the tighter band excludes boundary items that are easiest for the probe to classify, reducing discriminability at both the hidden-state and output levels. However, the gap remains positive for all models, and for Llama (+0.188) and Qwen2.5 (+0.285) it remains large (Appendix E). The qualitative finding—that hidden-state probes outperform single-pass output readouts—does not depend on the threshold choice, but the quantitative gap estimates should be interpreted with the D-band definition in mind.

5.2 Mechanistic Interpretations

Our results establish that the K-D signal is present in hidden states and substantially attenuated at the output, but they do not identify the responsible mechanism. The interpretations below are speculative hypotheses consistent with our data, offered to structure future investigation rather than as established conclusions. None is directly tested in this paper.

The next-token training objective may not reward reliability encoding at the output level (Allen-Zhu & Li, 2023): both K and D items are rewarded for producing the correct token when they get it right, and penalized equally when they do not. The architecture-specific attenuation patterns suggest that the bottleneck may differ across model families. One possibility is that the output projection is low-rank relative to the subspace encoding K-D separation (Zou et al., 2023). The softmax operation and sampling procedure may discard distributional structure that encodes reliability in low-probability tail tokens (Kuhn et al., 2023).

Token-level calibration may coexist with question-level miscalibration. Stolfo et al. (2024) identified dedicated confidence circuitry in transformer language models: entropy neurons that write to the unembedding null space and modulate output entropy via LayerNorm, and token frequency neurons that encode prior word frequencies. These circuits produce well-calibrated token-level predictions, but they operate at the granularity of individual next-token distributions, not at the question level where knowledge-gap recognition

is required. The propagation gap may thus reflect not the absence of confidence circuitry but a granularity mismatch: the architecture possesses mechanisms for calibrating distributional entropy over the next token but lacks a pathway to aggregate this signal into a question-level epistemic judgment that reaches the output.

The gap extends beyond binary correctness to continuous uncertainty signals. Kossen et al. (2024) showed that probes trained on hidden states from a single generation approximate semantic entropy—a quantity that normally requires multiple sampled generations to compute—with high fidelity. Their ablation studies identified specific layers and token positions where the semantic entropy signal is strongest, paralleling our finding that the K-vs-D signal peaks at middle layers. That two probe targets (correctness and semantic entropy) both show layer-specific encoding with output-level attenuation suggests the propagation gap is a general property of information flow in these architectures, not specific to any single operationalisation.

The architecture-specific attenuation patterns (Section 4.4) raise the possibility that late transformer layers actively compress the reliability signal in service of the generation task. The DoLA decoding strategy (Chuang et al., 2024) exploits exactly this contrast, recovering factuality information that the final layer discards. The three architectures with sufficient D sets show three distinct attenuation profiles—Mistral loses signal in late layers, Llama at both stages, Qwen2.5 almost entirely at readout—yet all three converge to similar output-level AUROC via different pathways, suggesting the bottleneck is a general property of the autoregressive output interface rather than a quirk of any single architecture.

Recent mechanistic interpretability work offers a candidate circuit-level explanation. Lindsey et al. (2025) used attribution graphs on Claude 3.5 Haiku to identify a default refusal circuit in which “unknown entity” features activate “can’t answer” features, and are suppressed when “known entity” features fire. Hallucination occurred when entity-level recognition suppressed the refusal circuit despite the model lacking the specific knowledge requested. This mechanism is consistent with the D-question overconfidence we observe: the model’s internal epistemic signal (analogous to the probe-accessible K-D separation in hidden states) is overridden by a coarser entity-recognition signal before it reaches the output. The propagation gap may thus reflect not passive information loss but active suppression by recognition circuits that operate at a coarser granularity than the underlying epistemic representation.

Several architectural proposals—deep supervision (Jolicoeur-Martineau, 2025), learnable residual weights (Heddes et al., 2025), and attention-based residual connections (Wang et al., 2026)—predict that selective layer access should close the propagation gap by reducing dilution of layer-specific information, but remain untested against the K-D reliability signal specifically.

5.3 Limitations

Several constraints bear on interpretation. D set sizes are small: 42–95 items for Tier 1 (61 for Qwen2.5), 3–24 for Tier 2. Even the largest D set (Llama, $N_D = 95$) limits the precision of per-layer AUROC estimates. Gemma’s anomalous probe profile (peak at L0, probe $N_D = 19$) may reflect sample-size constraints rather than a genuine architectural difference. A post-hoc power analysis using the Hanley & McNeil (1982) variance formula for AUROC confirms that the study is adequately powered under the default D band: all three models with gap tests exceed 99.9% power, with minimum detectable gaps (MDG at 80% power) of at most 0.096 AUROC against observed gaps of 0.178–0.243. Under the narrower 25–75 band, Llama and Qwen2.5 remain adequately powered (>99.9%), but Mistral ($N_D = 48$, gap = +0.070) falls below its MDG of 0.098, consistent with the reduced D-set size rather than absence of the effect.

The K/D/C labels are derived from 10 stochastic runs, and items near the thresholds are subject to binomial sampling noise. A question with true accuracy 0.85 has $P(\geq 9/10 \text{ correct}) \approx 0.35$ under a binomial model, so a non-trivial fraction of boundary items will be assigned K rather than D (or vice versa) by chance. This adds noise to the D set but does not systematically bias the probe in either direction: misclassified items lie near the K-D boundary where the distinction is weakest, and the probe is trained on the full set rather than on boundary items alone. The bootstrap gap tests, which resample items rather than relabelling them, are conservative in the presence of such noise because boundary items contribute less discriminative signal per resample. A threshold sensitivity analysis (Appendix E) confirms that the propagation gap remains positive under a narrower D band (25–75%).

CI-Bench v1 is a single benchmark of 338 factual questions. We have not tested whether the propagation gap generalizes to other QA datasets (Hendrycks et al., 2021; Lin et al., 2022b), to non-factual domains, or to longer-form tasks. The K/D/C taxonomy assumes single-turn factual questions with unambiguous ground-truth answers. Song et al. (2025) reported that internal-state probing excels at detecting factual inconsistencies but fails on logical fallacies, with Chain-of-Thought verification showing the inverse pattern. Our propagation gap results are established on factual QA—the domain where probing is strongest by their analysis—and whether the gap extends to logical or inferential tasks remains an open question.

The coverage category (C) mixes two construction regimes that are not homogeneous in activation space, as our surface-form controls demonstrated. CI-Bench v2 should disentangle coverage types that are lexically confounded from those that are not.

The logit probe uses nine summary features. Richer functionals, including attention to the full vocabulary distribution, might narrow the propagation gap. We emphasize that two structurally different single-pass readouts converge to the same ceiling, which constrains but does not eliminate this possibility.

Servedio et al. (2025) caution that factuality-probing results on synthetic true/false datasets may not generalise to realistic conditions. Our K-D labels are derived from behavioural screening on TriviaQA questions under stochastic sampling, which addresses their concern about synthetic data, but generality to other realistic datasets remains to be tested.

Tier 2 models appear only in behavioural screening, without hidden-state access. GPT-4o’s atypical D-accuracy pattern (91.3%, with negative overconfidence) warrants follow-up analysis with interpretability access to determine whether highly capable models exhibit a qualitatively different propagation profile.

6 Conclusion

We introduced CI-Bench, a factual benchmark with model-relative knowledge labels, and used it to demonstrate three findings. First, expressed confidence is informationally flat across the K-D boundary in four of six models with sufficient D items, with a fifth (Llama) showing partial but insufficient sensitivity. Second, hidden-state activations encode a moderate K-vs-D reliability signal (AUROC 0.74–0.76) that is linearly decodable and concentrated in middle transformer layers. Third, this signal is attenuated at the output: two structurally different single-pass readouts converge to a low ceiling (AUROC \approx 0.49–0.58), yielding a statistically significant propagation gap of 0.18–0.24 AUROC.

These results independently confirm the propagation gap reported by concurrent work (Gekhman et al., 2025; Park et al., 2025), with two methodological additions: a surface-form confound audit showing that C-vs-D probe separation is artefactual, and a ceiling convergence result constraining explanations for the output-level bottleneck.

CI-Bench and the labelling protocol are released. On single-turn factual QA, the propagation gap is a consistent property of the architectures we tested; whether it extends to reasoning tasks, longer generations, or multi-turn interactions remains open. Until it is closed, deployed systems that rely on expressed confidence for selective trust operate on an attenuated signal for the cases where trust matters most.

7 Methods

7.1 Models

We screened seven models in two tiers. Tier 1 (open-weight, hidden-state access): Mistral 7B Instruct v0.3 (Jiang et al., 2023) (32 layers, 4096-dim), Llama 3.1 8B Instruct (Dubey et al., 2024) (32 layers, 4096-dim), Gemma 2 9B IT (Gemma Team, 2024) (42 layers, 3584-dim), and Qwen2.5 7B Instruct (Team, 2025) (28 layers, 3584-dim). Tier 2 (API-only): GPT-4o (2024-08-06) (OpenAI, 2024), Gemini 2.5 Flash (Gemini Team, 2024), and Claude Sonnet 3.5 (Anthropic, 2024). All Tier 1 models were run locally using MLX with 4-bit quantization. Tier 2 models were accessed via their respective APIs.

7.2 Stochastic Screening and Confidence Elicitation

Each question was administered 10 times per model at temperature $T = 0.7$ (a moderate value balancing stochastic variation with deployment-realistic settings) with a maximum of 512 generated tokens. The 10-run accuracy profile determined the K/D/C label for each model-question pair.

Expressed confidence was measured using a dedicated V4 calibration prompt (Appendix A) that requests a 0–100 integer score, extracted by regex and normalized to $[0, 1]$. The V4 prompt achieved >99% extraction rate for all Tier 1 models; non-conforming responses (<1%, at most 3 items per model) were excluded. Tier 2 models used the same prompt via their respective APIs.

7.3 Activation Probing

For each Tier 1 model, we extracted hidden-state activations at every transformer layer (including the embedding layer, L0) for all 338 questions at the last token position, producing a d_{model} -dimensional vector per layer per question.

Linear probes. L2-regularized logistic regression ($C = 1.0$, balanced class weights, lbfgs solver), 5-fold stratified cross-validation, z-score normalized features. Applied independently at each layer for K-vs-D, C-vs-D, and K-vs-C contrasts.

Continuous reliability probe. Ridge regression (α by cross-validation) predicting proportion correct across 10 runs. Spearman ρ between predicted and observed reliability at each layer. **MLP probes.** Two-hidden-layer MLP (256 units, ReLU, dropout 0.3), same data splits. Tests whether additional capacity recovers nonlinear K-vs-D structure. **Shuffled-label baselines.** 10 permutation replicates per model at the best layer. K/D labels shuffled before training.

Surface-form controls. (1) Layer-0 probes: logistic regression on embedding-layer activations. (2) TF-IDF: bag-of-words classifier (500 features, logistic regression). (3) Surface features: logistic regression on seven hand-crafted variables. (4) Grouped cross-validation: training on C1 (temporal) questions, testing on C2 (obscurity), and vice versa.

7.4 Output-Level Probing

Logit probe. Logistic regression on nine summary features extracted from a single forward pass under two prompt conditions (answer prompt and V4 confidence prompt). Same regularization and normalization as hidden-state probes. **Behavioural features.** Variant A: single-pass verbalized confidence (one feature). Variant B: adds answer diversity (Shannon entropy over response distribution and count of unique answers across 10 runs). **Layer trajectory.** K-vs-D AUROC traced across four stages: best hidden layer, final hidden layer, logit probe, single-pass verbalized confidence.

7.5 Statistical Analysis

All classification performance is reported as AUROC on cross-validated held-out predictions. Bootstrap 95% CIs use the percentile method ($N = 1,000$ for individual estimates, $N = 5,000$ for paired gap tests). Paired bootstrap gap tests compare AUROC between pipeline stages on the same resampled indices; P -values are one-sided (proportion of resamples where the gap ≤ 0). Shuffled-label baselines provide non-parametric null distributions. Each paired gap test addresses a prespecified question about signal attenuation; we report all P -values without correction for multiple comparisons.

Broader Impact Statement

Identifying that models cannot surface their own reliability signal has direct implications for any deployed system relying on expressed confidence for selective trust; we see no negative societal impact from releasing the benchmark and analysis tools.

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A V4 Calibration Prompt

```

Question: {question}
You must respond in EXACTLY this format (two lines, nothing else):
Answer: <your answer here>
Confidence: <number from 0 to 100>

Do NOT put the confidence number first. Do NOT add explanation. Just the two lines
above.
```

B CI-Bench Question Examples

Table 4 shows representative questions from each CI-Bench sub-category.

C Extended Results

C.1 Per-Model Calibration Metrics

Table 5 reports per-model calibration metrics for all seven architectures. Confidence and accuracy are mean values across the V4 screening run. The K-D confidence gap and overconfidence on D items are the primary measures of uniform confidence.

Table 4: CI-Bench v1.0 question examples by category.

ID	Cat.	Question (truncated)	Answer
K-001	K	In a famous speech by Churchill on 4 June 1940 ... he went on to say “we shall fight” where else?	In the hills
K-010	K	Which Frenchman, a football administrator and head of FIFA from 1921 to 1954, is regarded as the founder of the World Cup?	Jules Rimet
K-050	K	In which month is the Gaelic festival of Beltane traditionally celebrated?	May
D2-001	D	Which is the second largest bay in Britain?	Morecambe
D2-002	D	Who narrated the BBC television production of Paddington?	Michael Hordern
D2-003	D	Admiral Sir John Jellicoe commanded the British fleet at the Battle of Jutland ... who commanded the German fleet?	Nemaska
C1-001	C1	Who won the 2024 United States presidential election?	Donald Trump
C1-002	C1	Which country became the newest EU member state after 2023?	None (no accession)
C2-001	C2	What is the name of the mayor of Berwick-upon-Tweed as of 2023?	(Civil parish; no traditional mayor)
C2-002	C2	What is the population of Ystad municipality according to the 2023 census?	~31,000

Table 5: Per-model calibration metrics across seven architectures. Conf. = mean expressed confidence (0–1). Acc. = mean accuracy. Gap = K confidence minus D confidence. Overconf. = D confidence minus D accuracy.

Model	N_D	K items		D items		K-D gap	Overconf.
		Conf.	Acc.	Conf.	Acc.		
<i>Tier 1 (open-weight)</i>							
Mistral 7B	77	0.995	0.915	0.989	0.507	0.6 pp	48.3 pp
Llama 3.1 8B	95	0.910	0.769	0.712	0.301	19.8 pp	41.1 pp
Gemma 2 9B	42	0.999	0.991	0.970	0.548	2.9 pp	42.3 pp
Qwen2.5 7B	61	0.9926	0.887	0.9943	0.393	−0.2 pp	60.1 pp
<i>Tier 2 (API-only)</i>							
GPT-4o	24	0.947	1.000	0.557	0.913	39.0 pp	−35.7 pp
Gemini 2.5 Fl.	23	0.998	0.989	0.977	0.546	2.1 pp	43.2 pp
Sonnet 3.5	3	0.929	1.000	0.883	1.000	4.5 pp	−11.7 pp

GPT-4o’s negative overconfidence reflects a D set near the K boundary (D accuracy 91.3%). Sonnet’s three D items are too few for reliable comparison.

C.2 Paired Bootstrap Gap Tests

Table 6 reports paired bootstrap gap tests ($N = 5,000$ resamples) for the three models with sufficient D items and hidden-state access. Each row tests whether AUROC at one pipeline stage exceeds the next. Common question subsets: Mistral $n = 289$, Llama $n = 268$, Qwen2.5 $n = 256$.

Variant A = single-pass verbalized confidence. Variant B = confidence + answer diversity (10 runs). The total propagation gap (best layer \rightarrow Variant A) is significant at $P < 0.001$ for all three models. Variant B

Table 6: Paired bootstrap gap tests for the propagation pipeline. P -values are one-sided (proportion of resamples where gap ≤ 0).

Model	Comparison	Δ AUROC	95% CI	P
Mistral 7B	Best layer \rightarrow last layer	+0.069	[+0.013, +0.125]	0.008
	Best layer \rightarrow Variant A	+0.178	[+0.084, +0.266]	<0.001
	Best layer \rightarrow Variant B	+0.070	[-0.012, +0.150]	0.048
	Last layer \rightarrow logit probe	+0.045	[-0.048, +0.144]	0.173
	Logit probe \rightarrow Variant A	+0.063	[-0.046, +0.169]	0.127
Llama 3.1 8B	Best layer \rightarrow last layer	+0.075	[+0.019, +0.132]	0.006
	Best layer \rightarrow Variant A	+0.194	[+0.088, +0.297]	<0.001
	Best layer \rightarrow Variant B	+0.176	[+0.075, +0.273]	<0.001
	Last layer \rightarrow logit probe	+0.085	[-0.005, +0.171]	0.033
	Logit probe \rightarrow Variant A	+0.034	[-0.076, +0.152]	0.277
Qwen2.5 7B	Best layer \rightarrow last layer	+0.029	[-0.050, +0.111]	0.249
	Best layer \rightarrow Variant A	+0.243	[+0.134, +0.350]	0.0002
	Last layer \rightarrow logit probe	+0.149	[+0.040, +0.258]	0.004

rows are omitted for Qwen2.5 because Variant B requires 10 forward passes, placing it outside the single-pass scope of the propagation gap definition (Equation 3).

C.3 Surface-Form Control Detail

Table 7 reports surface-form control results. Non-neural controls (TF-IDF, surface features, grouped CV) use original (non-model-relative) labels on the Mistral 7B question set ($n = 338$; $K = 210$, $D = 89$, $C = 39$). The hidden-state probe and layer-0 rows use V4 model-relative labels to match the probing analysis in Section 4.2.

Table 7: Surface-form control analysis. AUROC reported as mean \pm std over 5-fold CV. The K-vs-D signal survives all controls; the C-vs-D signal does not.

Control method	C-vs-D	K-vs-D	K-vs-C
Hidden-state probe (best layer)	0.99–1.00	0.742	0.96–0.99
Layer-0 embeddings	0.90–0.99	0.26–0.47	0.90–0.97
TF-IDF (500 features)	0.945 \pm 0.048	0.596 \pm 0.065	0.951 \pm 0.024
Surface features (7 vars.)	0.829 \pm 0.091	0.440 \pm 0.054	0.811 \pm 0.088
Grouped CV (C1 \leftrightarrow C2)	0.65–0.92	0.41–0.67	—

Year-string presence explains the C-vs-D shortcut: 64% of C questions contain four-digit year strings (matching `\b20[12]\d\b`), compared with 0% of D questions and 2% of K questions. Mean digit count: $C = 3.72$, $D = 1.43$, $K = 1.43$.

D Reproducibility

Table 8 summarises the reproducibility posture of this work. CI-Bench questions, experiment code, analysis pipelines, and all result files (including hidden-state activations and per-run model responses) are released in the supplementary repository and as a companion data archive (<https://github.com/raeq/propagation-gap>). The full results directory (~ 273 MB) is available as a compressed archive; activation files are stored as NumPy `.npz` arrays. All experiments were conducted on consumer hardware (Apple M-series, no GPU cluster).

Figure 1: **A model-relative taxonomy reveals depth ignorance invisible to standard benchmarks.** (A) CI-Bench construction overview. Each question is administered to a model 10 times under temperature sampling; the stochastic accuracy profile assigns a model-relative label: Known (K, $\geq 90\%$), Depth-ignorant (D, 20–80%), or Coverage-ignorant (C, $< 20\%$). (B) Label distributions across seven models. D rates range from 0.9% (Sonnet) to 28.1% (Llama). Tier 2 models convert most items to K. (C) D rates across seven models. The inverse relationship between model capability and D rate is consistent with stronger models converting D items to K rather than eliminating them. (D) D-set overlap. No question is classified D by all seven models (Jaccard index 0.31 for the two largest D sets, Llama and Mistral). Depth ignorance is a property of the model-question interaction, not a fixed attribute of questions. $n = 338$ questions per model; 10 stochastic runs per question.

E Threshold Sensitivity

The K/D/C labels depend on the accuracy thresholds used to define the D band (default: 20–80%). To test whether the propagation gap is robust to this choice, we re-ran the probing analysis under a narrower D band (25–75%). A wider band (30–80%) produced identical D sets because no items in these datasets have stochastic accuracy in the 75–80% or 25–30% ranges; we therefore report only the two distinct configurations.

Narrowing the D band from 20–80 to 25–75 reduces N_D substantially (e.g., Mistral: 77→48) and attenuates the gap for Mistral (+0.146→+0.070), but the gap remains positive for all models. Llama and Qwen2.5 retain gaps of +0.188 and +0.285 respectively. The qualitative finding—that hidden-state probes outperform single-pass output readouts—is not an artefact of a particular threshold choice.

Figure 2: **Expressed confidence carries negligible information about knowledge state.** (A) Calibration scatter for four Tier 1 models. K items cluster at high confidence and high accuracy. D items cluster at high confidence but variable accuracy. (B) Confidence distributions for K versus D items (Mistral 7B). Gap: 0.6 percentage points, despite a 40.9-point accuracy gap. (C) K-to-D confidence gap across models. Four of seven models show gaps below 3 pp despite accuracy gaps exceeding 40 pp. (D) Accuracy gap versus confidence gap. Llama (19.8 pp) is a partial exception; GPT-4o’s reversed pattern reflects a residual D set near the K boundary (D accuracy 91.3%).

Figure 6 shows statistical power as a function of N_D for each model under both threshold bands. Under the default band, all three models exceed 99.9% power. Under the narrow band, Mistral falls below 80% power ($N_D = 48$, observed gap = +0.070), while Llama and Qwen2.5 remain adequately powered.

Figure 3: **Hidden representations encode a linearly decodable reliability signal.** (A) Per-layer K-vs-D AUROC for four open-weight models (5-fold stratified CV). Mistral peaks at 0.742 (L16), Llama at 0.764 (L15), and Qwen2.5 at 0.736 (L17); all three concentrate discriminability in the middle-to-upper portion of the transformer stack. Gemma peaks at 0.699 (L0), likely reflecting its smaller probe D set ($N_D = 19$). (B) Best-layer AUROC for three binary contrasts. C-vs-D is near-perfect (>0.99) but driven by surface-form confounds (see Figure 4). (C) Continuous reliability probe: Llama $\rho = 0.424$, tracking its higher binary probe ceiling. (D) MLP vs. linear probe: mean $\Delta = -0.053$ across four models. The K-vs-D boundary is approximately linear. (E) Shuffled-label baselines: $3.0\text{--}9.0\sigma$ ($P < 0.001$ for all models).

Figure 4: **C-vs-D probe separation is driven by surface-form cues in the input.** (A) C-vs-D AUROC remains high under TF-IDF (0.945) and surface-feature classifiers (0.829), both without access to model activations. K-vs-D AUROC falls to 0.596 (TF-IDF) and 0.440 (surface features). (B) Grouped cross-validation: training on C1 and testing on C2 (or vice versa) reduces C-vs-D AUROC to 0.65–0.92 but leaves K-vs-D in the range 0.41–0.67. (C) C-vs-D saturates within 20 training examples, consistent with a surface-form shortcut. K-vs-D shows no such saturation.

Table 8: Reproducibility checklist.

Item	Status	Location / Note
CI-Bench questions (338)	Released	<code>data/questions/</code>
Experiment code	Released	<code>experiments/</code>
Analysis pipelines	Released	<code>analysis/</code>
Canonical result JSONs	Released	<code>results/</code>
Hidden-state activations	Released	<code>activations/</code> (GitHub release)
Per-run model responses	Released	<code>data/responses/</code>
V4 calibration prompt	In manuscript	Section 7
Model names & versions	Specified	Section 7
Quantization	Specified	MLX 4-bit (Tier 1)
Probe hyperparameters	Specified	$C = 1.0$, balanced weights, lbfgs
Cross-validation	Specified	5-fold stratified, z -score norm
Random seed	Specified	<code>random_state=42</code>
Bootstrap resamples	Specified	$N = 5,000$ (gap tests), $N = 1,000$ (CIs)
Temperature	Specified	$T = 0.7$, 10 runs per question
Hardware	Specified	Apple Silicon (M-series); no GPU cluster
Dependencies	Released	<code>pyproject.toml</code>

Figure 5: **The reliability signal is substantially attenuated between hidden states and the output.**

(A) Layer trajectory. Mistral loses signal primarily in late layers (L16→L32: -0.069 , $P = 0.008$). Llama attenuates at both stages (L15→L32: -0.075 , $P = 0.006$; L32→logit: -0.085 , $P = 0.033$). Qwen2.5 preserves signal through late layers but loses it at readout (L28→logit: $+0.149$, $P = 0.004$). (B) Internal vs. output AUROC: gap of 0.18–0.24 across three models. (C) Paired bootstrap ($N = 5,000$): Mistral $+0.178$ ($P < 0.001$); Llama $+0.194$ ($P < 0.001$); Qwen2.5 $+0.243$ ($P = 0.0002$). (D) Single-pass readout comparison. Logit probe vs. verbalized confidence: neither difference reaches significance. Both fall well below the hidden-state ceiling.

Table 9: Propagation gap under alternative D-band thresholds. Hidden = best-layer K-vs-D AUROC (5-fold CV). Behav. = single-pass verbalized confidence AUROC. Gap = Hidden – Behav. Values are from a standalone threshold-sensitivity pipeline and may differ slightly from the paired bootstrap estimates in Table 6, which use resampled common-subset indices. The propagation gap is positive for all models under both threshold bands.

D band	Model	N_D	Hidden	Behav.	Gap
20–80 (default)	Mistral 7B	77	0.732	0.586	+0.146
	Llama 3.1 8B	95	0.843	0.607	+0.235
	Qwen2.5 7B	61	0.727	0.514	+0.213
25–75 (narrow)	Mistral 7B	48	0.706	0.637	+0.070
	Llama 3.1 8B	58	0.804	0.616	+0.188
	Qwen2.5 7B	28	0.792	0.506	+0.285

Figure 6: Post-hoc power analysis for the propagation gap. Power to detect the observed gap (best hidden – Variant A AUROC) is plotted as a function of N_D for each model under the default (20–80) and narrow (25–75) D bands. Dashed line: 80% power threshold. Variance estimated via the Hanley–McNeil formula with assumed inter-estimator correlation $r = 0.5$.